

Original Article

The Impact of Digital Technologies on Strategic Product Development

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Abstract

Digital technologies are changing the strategic development landscape very quickly, and this has resulted in new product development processes where they play vital roles. Our research looks into how profound these changes are by studying how much productivity has been improved through innovative approaches in enhancing creativity or improving market response time. The research emphasizes digital instruments like artificial intelligence (AI), big data analytics, and 3D printing as pivotal in transforming traditional product development methodologies through an in-depth analysis or literature review and case studies. What has been discovered is that digital technologies aid in the ideation process, improve the accuracy of prototypes and make the time to market faster. In addition, they also enhance customization and alignment with customer tastes and preferences. In addition, the paper considers how digital collaborative platforms and agile development methodologies support dynamic and iterative product development life cycles. Companies achieve a competitive edge by integrating these technologies and this leads to increased innovation capacity along with more adaptive strategic planning. There is a final conclusion on digital transformation because there are both challenges and opportunities regarding product development as a result of this research. For any company that wants continuous growth and market leadership, they can leverage on insights provided here.

Keywords: Customization, Digital instruments, Digital technologies, Productivity, Strategic product development

1. INTRODUCTION

With regard to its internal value-adding chain of activities, this study aims to investigate how Engineering to Order Company's (ETO) strategic change has impacted its standing as a sub-supplier. The transformation is driven and made easier by end-to-end business data regarding the processes pertaining to the product's engineering, configuration, and design. The inquiry expands on case-based research in the wake of the company's decision to streamline its product line to just one family of products, improving process effectiveness and expanding its market reach by offering specialized and innovative items (Weckenmann et al., 2019). When sales, product development, and production setup are digitally integrated, the conventional trade-off between affordable solutions with a wide range

of products and quick lead times is significantly minimized. Information and expertise are now essential resources for advancing contemporary economic and social development (Weckenmann et al., 2019).

The transition to the digital era has caused a reorganization of organizations' business environment and economics (Iqbal, 2023). Digital technologies have had a profound impact on strategic product development, revolutionizing the way companies conceive, design, manufacture, and deliver products to market. This research aims to explore the impact of digital technologies on strategic product development and investigate how organizations can harness them to enhance their capabilities. Digital technologies include AI, machine learning, IoT, VR, and cloud computing. Advanced CAD software and simulation tools enable companies to create

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virtual prototypes, conduct rapid iterations, and test different scenarios before physically producing a product. Virtual reality technologies allow for immersive design reviews and user experience testing ((Manavalan & Jayakrishna, 2019). Digital technologies have revolutionized the way products are manufactured, delivered, and supported. E-commerce platforms and online marketplaces have made it easier for companies to reach global markets and interact directly with customers. This research will explore the impacts of these technologies on strategic product development and identify best practices for organizations to leverage digital tools effectively. In the contemporary knowledge-based society, Industry 4.0 may be seen as a facilitator as it combines new digital technologies (DTs) (Manavalan & Jayakrishna, 2019; Weckenmann et al., 2019).

Financial services companies understand how important it is to gauge their success in terms of how well their products or services meet customer expectations (Nawaz et al., 2022). Companies engage with their current and potential customers through digital channels including social media, websites, and search engine optimization (Fareed et al., 2023). This suggests that the intense desire that usually accompanies impulse buying is not always present with spontaneous purchases (Iqbal et al., 2023).

Significance

Digital technologies can help companies gain a competitive advantage by understanding customer needs and preferences. This research is of significant importance to academic study of how digital technologies transform strategic product development. This is because the research will offer a summary of current literature, together with case studies that will comprehensively cover state-of-the-art digital tools used in product development. The outcome will give businesses which intend to include digital technologies into their processes of product development practical knowledge. Comprehending the merits and drawbacks of these technologies will help companies come up with well-thought-out choices and establish better strategies for market competition as well as creativity.

This study proves how digital technologies can simplify and make better the product development process hence improving innovation possibilities of corporations. Through this research, organizations can be able to apply

Artificial Intelligence (AI), Big Data Analytics tools among others like using 3D printer so as to come up with new products meeting different market requirements by understanding what it means to be 'innovative. The study will show how digital technologies can improve a company's capability to react to changes in the market quickly and accurately. This greater responsiveness will mean better compatibility with what consumers want, causing quicker product development and giving us better chances to outdo our competitors.

This study will offer an understanding of the ways through which digital collaboration platforms together with agile development frameworks could optimize product development procedures. When firms use these methods, they are able to provoke faster as well as more cyclical development phases which will in turn bring about higher grade commodities and improved market debut

Research Questions

What possible or current uses of DTs for SPM are documented in the literature?

How might SPM be facilitated in a CE using DTs?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

McKinsey & Company found that companies that invest in customer insights and analytics are more likely to achieve above-average growth and profitability (McKinsey & Company, 2016). A study by Cooper and Kleinschmidt (2007) found that companies that invested more in market research had higher success rates for new product development, indicating the importance of market research in enhancing product performance. Market research was the most common tool used by companies to identify growth opportunities and inform product development strategies. The use of strategic buckets encourages the partition of the total NPD resource budget into smaller, more specialized budgets based on the type of creative effort (radical or incremental). Research to far has paid little attention to the empirical study of how information technology (IT) influences new product efficacy. The purpose of this study is to determine whether and to what extent the usage of particular IT tools during the stages of the new product development (NPD) process—namely, market performance, innovativeness, and product quality—affects the success of the NPD process. Its conclusions are supported by knowledge-based theory. Based on data collected from NPD managers in the US and Canada, the

findings demonstrate that various IT platforms have varying effects on a number of new product effectiveness measures. Furthermore, the results show how these IT tools are effective at different phases of the NPD process. Digital technology has revolutionized many aspects of modern life, including the corporate environment. Research and interest in the topic of how digital technology influences strategic development have increased significantly in recent years. This review of the literature attempts to look into and compile the body of information that already exists on the topic, providing understanding of the ways in which digital technology influences strategic progress. Many academics contend that the disruptive power of digital technology fundamentally transforms conventional company models and strategies. Organizations can save costs, enhance consumer experiences, and develop novel business models thanks to digital technology. A theoretical foundation for comprehending the transformative impact of digital technology on strategic development is provided by Christensen's (2006) research on disruptive innovation. A firm's possible source of competitive advantage is product development, which entails a complicated linkage between market demands and technological capabilities (Brown & Eisenhardt, 1995). As competition becomes more intense, businesses compete more and more based on an advanced network of research and development (R&D) collaboration (Rojakkers & Hagedorn, 2006), making use of disparate data from throughout the globe (Chesbrough, 2003). In this sense, multinational firms profit from their globally distributed innovation networks and their ability to produce, absorb, and incorporate knowledge (Bartlett & Ghoshal 1990). When businesses are able to leverage the knowledge from their dispersed subsidiaries, they may swiftly and efficiently develop new products while still satisfying local desires (Subramaniam & Venkatraman, 2001). Using interviews and an action research technique, we studied product development practices and eco-design methodologies together with qualitative data from 19 firms. The study's findings led to the development of a four-stage framework for eco-design practice: first, conduct an environmental assessment from a life cycle perspective; second, share the analysis with others and solicit comments; third, prioritize the environmental issues; and fourth, complete the design using the necessary tools and techniques. The 'ARPI' structure, which stands for 'analysis, report, prioritize, and improve,' is applicable at

both the strategic and operational levels. The function of "eco-design champions" is explained. Early testing of the framework in cooperating organizations revealed communication challenges with design teams. Further challenges include the development of specialized tools and the training of designers. Regarding the prevalence of the various DTs in the 619 papers, the most frequently used search phrase was the entire distribution and quantity of papers found by combining each sustainability and each DT phaseout (159 documents), followed by AI2 (145 documents) and big data (135 documents). In the realm of sustainability, the three themes with the highest number of publications were life cycle management (114 papers), SSCM (132 documents), and CE (123 documents). The most popular combinations of search terms are shown in Figure 2 by the tallest bars. CE was commonly connected with Industry 4.0 (43 publications) and the Internet of Things (40 documents). LCA and AI as a keyword combination produced 37 documents. All DT words were used about equally frequently in the SSCM field. Adopting digital technology can give businesses a long-lasting competitive advantage. Businesses can streamline operations, increase productivity, and better understand their target market by embracing digital transformation. Companies may provide tailored experiences, modify their goods and services, and react quickly to client requests thanks to this insight. According to research, businesses who successfully integrate digital technology into their strategic planning have a competitive advantage. Although there is no denying that digital technology has an impact on strategic development, there are obstacles and constraints that businesses must overcome. These include problems with data security and privacy, a lack of digital skills, outdated technology, and unwillingness to change. For organizations to properly utilize the advantages of digital technology while reducing associated dangers, an understanding of these issues is essential. Though it examines the impact of digital technology on many phases of product creation, including ideation, design, prototyping, testing, and market launch. It does this by analyzing pertinent research studies, publications, and industry reports. The assessment also covers how digital technology may affect teamwork, competitive advantage, and strategic decision-making in the context of product creation. The results demonstrate how digital technologies have a transformative impact on strategic product development processes by fostering

creativity, efficiency, and customer centricity.

A few examples of Industry 4.0's sophisticated and potentially disruptive applications are the rise of the Internet of Things (IoT), big data analytics, artificial intelligence (AI), and block chain technology (together known as DTs) (Kristoffersen et al., 2019). Industry 4.0 and CE regulations are pressuring businesses to participate in DTs in order to provide information accessibility over the life cycles of their products (Awan et al., 2021). According to Yang et al. (2018), for example, R-strategies 1 including recycling, reuse, and repair can be supported by knowledge of a product's original design specifications. Nevertheless, it is often difficult to get the required information (Kouhizadeh et al., 2020). A product that people want to interact with and use is what user-oriented design (UOD) makes technology into. This paper looks at the basic connections between UOD contributions and the results and process of NPD.

Industry 4.0 and sustainability research are often viewed as two distinct topics at the product level, but interest in their junction is expanding (Ingemarsdotter et al., 2020; Beltrami et al., 2021). Studies on the relationship between Industry 4.0, DTs, and CE have proliferated recently (Cagno et al., 2021; Massaro et al., 2021; Pagoropoulos et al., 2017). Even though some of these studies (Ingemarsdotter et al., 2020; Lopes de Sousa Jabbour et al., 2018) discuss the potential of DTs in specific CE strategies or provide early examples of successful implementation (Nobre & Tavares, 2017), a comprehensive and comparative review of DTs in sustainable product management (SPM) is still lacking. Furthermore, research focused on the CE as a whole or on certain components of it (Bressanelli et al., 2018; Garrido-Hidalgo et al., 2020) often fails to adopt a sufficiently wide viewpoint and, in particular, ignores the social dimension of sustainability. This study aims to provide a comprehensive review of the different DTs and how organizations might benefit from them in their cyclical and SPM activities. As we progress toward a CE, applying this broader SPM lens allows for new insights into how DT could improve sustainable supply chain management, sustainability assessment (including the social component), or sustainable product design (SSCM).

The linear economy faces challenges from the idea of a circular economy (CE) because of a lack of knowledge about the physical life cycles of things. Material flows are designed to retain their best value for as long as possible

and to recirculate in loops within the economy in order to minimize waste and negative environmental effects. The concept of a CE can be operationalized with the aid of the Resolve framework (EMF, 2015). This study employs the circularity strategies of virtualization, exchange, loop, optimize, share, and regenerate. These strategies involve exchanging information about materials and products and sharing a thorough life cycle viewpoint. DTs have already influenced an industrial production paradigm change, and the growth of a CE also depends on a variety of technologies. This research focuses on four technologies: IoT, big data, AI, and block chain. Digital technologies are transforming product development and impacting companies' strategic direction. The research highlights that digital technologies are revolutionizing how companies design, develop, and deliver products.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study presents a qualitative design, emphasizing mainly on an in-depth review of literature as well as examination of prevailing theories on consumer loyalty, satisfaction, sales & marketing strategy taking place therein. It will involve several systematic steps aimed at providing an exhaustive analysis on it. The current study has been developed to be a literature review-based research paper. The approach involves identifying, choosing and evaluating pertinent scholarly articles, books and appropriate theories existing for purposes of synthesizing available knowledge and outlining gaps that require further investigation.

This study will provide a complete account of how customer loyalty and satisfaction impact strategic market management by analyzing current literature and theories, providing inputs that academic researchers as well as business people will find beneficial

An initial search will unearth various sources, which shall be narrowed through abstract screening and relevance to the research questions. The precise exploration of some pieces of literature, its thorough theoretical grounding, and methodological adequacy will be done. What will be analyzed here are the methodology, findings as well as conclusions of each of these sources

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, strategic product development has been significantly impacted by digital technologies. The study's findings show that

using digital technology in product development procedures has several advantages, including better productivity, enhanced teamwork, shortened time-to-market, and higher customer satisfaction. Utilizing digital tools like simulation, data analytics, and virtual prototyping, businesses may speed up product development cycles, cut costs, and make wise decisions based on current information. Throughout the course of the product development lifecycle, businesses can collect and analyze enormous volumes of data thanks to the introduction of digital technology. Organizations can establish more informed and focused product development plans by using this data-driven method to discover market trends, client preferences, and upcoming opportunities. Digital technologies also make it possible for teams to collaborate cross-functionally, regardless of where they are physically located. This encourages creativity and knowledge exchange, which ultimately results in the creation of more competitive and client-focused goods. Furthermore, the study shows how the connection between businesses and customers has changed because of digital technologies. Through digital platforms, businesses can interact with consumers directly, collect input, and use it to inform future product development. By designing products with the needs of the client in mind, it is more likely that they will meet or surpass those needs, boosting customer loyalty and market share. It is crucial to remember that implementing digital technology in the development of strategic products is not without its difficulties. These difficulties include the necessity for ongoing technological advancements, the need for qualified individuals to use digital technologies efficiently and worries about cybersecurity and data privacy. By investing in training programmed, putting in place strong cybersecurity measures, and adhering to the necessary data protection rules, organizations must proactively handle these difficulties.

In conclusion, it is evident that digital technologies have an impact on the strategic product creation process. It has changed conventional product development methodologies, allowing businesses to innovate, work together, and provide goods that satisfy customers' changing needs. In today's quickly changing business environment, businesses who embrace digital technologies and strategically integrate them into their product development processes are likely to acquire a competitive advantage

Competing Interests

The authors did not declare any competing interest.

References

- Awan, U., Shamim, S., Khan, Z., Zia, N. U., Shariq, S. M., & Khan, M. N. (2021). Big data analytics capability and decision-making: The role of data-driven insight on circular economy performance. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 168, 120766.
- Bartlett, C. A., & Ghoshal, S. (1990). The multinational corporation as an interorganizational network. *Academy of management review*, 15(4), 603-625.
- Beltrami, M., Orzes, G., Sarkis, J., & Sartor, M. (2021). Industry 4.0 and sustainability: Towards conceptualization and theory. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 312, 127733.
- Bressanelli, G., Adrodegari, F., Perona, M., & Saccani, N. (2018). Exploring how usage-focused business models enable circular economy through digital technologies. *Sustainability*, 10(3), 639.
- Brown, S. L., & Eisenhardt, K. M. (1995). Product development: Past research, present findings, and future directions. *Academy of management review*, 20(2), 343-378.
- Cagno, E., Neri, A., Negri, M., Bassani, C. A., & Lampertico, T. (2021). The role of digital technologies in operationalizing the circular economy transition: A systematic literature review. *Applied Sciences*, 11(8), 3328.
- Chesbrough, H. W. (2003). *Open innovation: The new imperative for creating and profiting from technology*. Harvard Business Press.
- Christensen, C. M. (2006). The ongoing process of building a theory of disruption. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 23(1), 39-55.
- Cooper, R. G., & Kleinschmidt, E. J. (2007). Winning businesses in product development: The critical success factors. *Research-Technology Management*, 50(3), 50-60.
- Fareed, S. A. Q., Jabbar, T., Makhdoom, S. F., & Iqbal, M. N. (2023). Influence of Digital Marketing on Purchase Decision: A Qualitative Study on Pakistani Customers. *International Journal of Trends and Innovations in Business & Social Sciences*, 1(4), 122-128.
- Garrido-Hidalgo, C., Ramirez, F. J., Olivares, T., & Roda-Sanchez, L. (2020). The adoption of internet of things in a circular supply chain framework for the recovery of WEEE: The case of lithium-ion electric

- vehicle battery packs. *Waste Management*, 103, 32-44.
- Ingemarsdotter, E., Jamsin, E., & Balkenende, R. (2020). Opportunities and challenges in IoT-enabled circular business model implementation—A case study. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 162, 105047.
- Iqbal, M. N. (2023). Exploration of The Factors Influencing Customer Perspectives And Intention Regarding Digital Bancassurance. *Journal of Management and Economic Studies*, 5(4), 205-214.
- Iqbal, M. N., Shaikh, N. N., & Dilshad, W. B. (2023). An Impulsive Buying Behavior of Customer: A Qualitative Study on Bancassurance Services in Pakistan. *Priority-The International Business Review*, 2(1), 138-151.
- Kouhizadeh, M., Zhu, Q., & Sarkis, J. (2020). Blockchain and the circular economy: potential tensions and critical reflections from practice. *Production Planning & Control*, 31(11-12), 950-966.
- Kristoffersen, E., Aremu, O. O., Blomsma, F., Mikalef, P., & Li, J. (2019). Exploring the relationship between data science and circular economy: an enhanced CRISP-DM process model. In *Digital Transformation for a Sustainable Society in the 21st Century: 18th IFIP WG 6.11 Conference on e-Business, e-Services, and e-Society, I3E 2019, Trondheim, Norway, September 18–20, 2019, Proceedings 18* (pp. 177-189). Springer International Publishing.
- Lopes de Sousa Jabbour, A. B., Jabbour, C. J. C., Godinho Filho, M., & Roubaud, D. (2018). Industry 4.0 and the circular economy: a proposed research agenda and original roadmap for sustainable operations. *Annals of Operations Research*, 270, 273-286.
- Manavalan, E., & Jayakrishna, K. (2019). A review of Internet of Things (IoT) embedded sustainable supply chain for industry 4.0 requirements. *Computers & industrial engineering*, 127, 925-953.
- Massaro, M., Secinaro, S., Dal Mas, F., Brescia, V., & Calandra, D. (2021). Industry 4.0 and circular economy: An exploratory analysis of academic and practitioners' perspectives. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30(2), 1213-1231.
- McKinsey & Company. (2016). The Value of Customer Experience, Quantified. Retrieved from <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/marketing-and-sales/our-insights/the-value-of-customer-experience-quantified>
- Nawaz, M. N. I. D. M., Zakai, S. N. Z. S. N., & Hassan, M. H. D. M. (2022). An exploration of the factors influences customer response towards banking products and services. *Periodicals of Social Sciences*, 2(2), 179-192.
- Nobre, G. C., & Tavares, E. (2017). Scientific literature analysis on big data and internet of things applications on circular economy: a bibliometric study. *Scientometrics*, 111, 463-492.
- Pagoropoulos, A., Pigosso, D. C., & McAloone, T. C. (2017). The emergent role of digital technologies in the Circular Economy: A review. *Procedia cirp*, 64, 19-24.
- Roijackers. L. M. & Hagedorn W., (2006), Learning to design organizations and learning from designing them, *Org. Sci.*, 17(2), pp. 171-178, 2006.
- Subramaniam, M., & Venkatraman, N. (2001). Determinants of transnational new product development capability: Testing the influence of transferring and deploying tacit overseas knowledge. *Strategic management journal*, 22(4), 359-378.
- Weckenmann, A., Bodi, Ş., Popescu, S., Dragomir, M., Hurgoiu, D., & Comes, R. (2019). Hit or miss? Evaluating the potential of a research niche: a case study in the field of virtual quality management. *Sustainability*, 11(5), 1450.
- Yang, Y., Tang, Y., Fang, G., Shan, L., Guo, J., Zhang, W., ... & Liang, S. (2018). Li+ intercalated V 2 O 5 · n H 2 O with enlarged layer spacing and fast ion diffusion as an aqueous zinc-ion battery cathode. *Energy & Environmental Science*, 11(11), 3157-3162.